

Mahatma Gandhi: A Dual Personality

Ananya Rai

B.A., LL.B (Hons), Indore Institute of Law
Indore, Madhya Pradesh, India

ABSTRACT

Mahatma Gandhi, the Father of the Nation is always an inspiring one for the people not only for India but people for all over the world. The gentlemen who was admired by the Martin Luther King Jr., Barack Obama and may more is now facing the number of criticism of Indian people. How one can criticize whose focus was only to see India develop. Thus, in this paper the researcher tries to throw light on the haters and the great critic of Gandhi who not only criticize him for the type of politics he followed but also on the basis of personal life he lived upon. There is always a great debate between the haters and lovers of Gandhi. In this paper, the researcher covered all sphere of Gandhi's life in starting from the working in Law Firm of South Africa to the 1947 independence of India. In between both, the paper includes the circumstances and the atmosphere and what Gandhi faced. In this paper, the researcher made the continuance efforts to made the reluctant things come in front and till what extent Gandhi's ideology is applicable in the present scenario.

Keywords: Mahatma Gandhi, ideology, politics, movements of India, criticism, British Raj

INTRODUCTION

"He never chooses an opinion; he just wears whatever happens to be in style."¹

– Leo Tolstoy

The aforementioned statement clearly elaborates the things, the first thing about the great person, the one who admired a lot not only by the Indian but from the people all over the world. But, the question rises in one's mind that how the person who is so acknowledged is became the tool of hatred by billions. The above stated fact clarify that the Father of the Nation never agree to other's thoughts and ideas rather he want to get his facts and thoughts first which signifies by the other part of the statement. The Indian history consists of bulk of extraordinary reformers and national leaders who sow a seed of modernity where the India is present today. The name of one such leader is the 'Father of the Nation', Mohandas Karamchand Gandhi who made a lot of efforts and sacrifice to make India free from British Raj. Not only this he had also responsible for the revolutionary change starting from the grass root level unlike, the leaders of today who only work on the surface and what is happening beyond the curtains it doesn't bother them. But, this man who served the nation for half of his life after coming from South Africa in 1901 made the dual reflection of his personality. Some people appreciate him and some criticize him. How it could be possible whose ideology of non-violence was widely accepted worldwide is now facing a great turmoil? After having sixty years of independence, the figure of Gandhi is considered double. It is a contrary, one side the peace and innocence picture is greatly worship and inspire the Nelson Mandela and Martin Luther King Jr. from his ideology and on the other he has been greatest picture of hatred among the young Indians. According to the Gandhi's grandson, the relationship taught by his father for Gandhi was that "the greatest father you can have but the one father I

¹ B Chandrashekar, Confession of Gandhi-Hater, Available at <<https://www.youthkiawaaz.com/2014/11/mahatma-gandhi-criticism/>>

wish I did not have."² What is the relevance of this statement? Do the nation's service and the "Father of the Nation" overshadowed the father of a child. Mahatma Gandhi had been greatly criticized on the basis of their personal life. The another thing with reference to Gandhi is that, the man is being called the light of fearlessness on one hand and on the other the concept of politics played by him was not follow at present day people and his way was politically ethical.

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

In this paper, the researcher throws the light starting from the Mahatma's invasion in India the incidence in Champaran to the independence of India. In this paper, the researcher focuses on the things which been hidden and not know to the people whether it is in favor of Gandhi or against. The paper also includes the idea of personal haters of Gandhi which is totally based on the personal life of Gandhi and with the same pace it includes the things which elaborate the concept of modernity and how it opposes strictly by him. The researcher tries to discuss the criticism and positive note both with the help of past speeches, conducts that had done by him which he not supposed to do and what must be in hands that not been performed by him.

THE NEW BEGINNING: GANDHI AND CHAMPARAN MOMENT

Chamapran Satyagrah was the first moment in accordance with the ideology of Gandhi .In 1917 in the Champaran district of Bihar the obnoxiously farmers were faced and forced to grow the blue-dye, indigo and this imposed suffering on him undoubtedly. But, in the path of the struggle, the most important step led by the intelligentsia by some of the most prominent leader in which of them was Mahatma Gandhi. He not only gains the support of the people but made them realize the importance of the independence nation. There was no other man, as Gandhi when the legal practitioner were charging extra fees was only in this moment when struggle again the hardship of English men started by the Indians through the motivation of none another but the Father of the Nation, i.e., Mahatma Gandhi. The statement made by Mahatma Gandhi when he saw the crowd outside the court room was very motivational. As after seeing the people outside the court room he

approximately said that yes we achieve as Indian's got the independence. made this statement as it was the only first time in India when all came up and fought for the same goal against the English people. As the question which revolves around on one's mind is that although there was numerous of efforts made by him but then how people the fountain of criticism made on him? He was the only one who started civil disobedience moment. Is the problem only related to political sphere or something was in personal life that generate the critic around.

Mr. MK Ganghi's politics has been criticized with the modern form of politics argue that for Gandhi the ground of moral action is fearlessness, while that of political reason is security and self defense. Gandhi sees that the context of the moral action in the mundane fabric of everyday life, especially in the place such as the families and the villages. For this reason Gandhi does not believe that moral action requires being supplemented by the particular kind of unity which politics and the state call for and necessitate. Thereby, Uday Mehta work on Gandhi draw out the reason for Gandhi's disagreement with the modern form of politics is interesting and find his argument gain plausible. Gandhi was criticized by many other including Uday Mehta, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar, Arundhati Roy Dr. Kusoom Vadgama and many youngsters in India.³

INDEPENENCE MOMENT AND GANDHI'S STRUGGLE

Gandhi's leadership started from Champaran district in 1917 when he supported indigo-planters to fought against the unreasonable and hardship of Britishers. The Rowlatt Act turned him into all Indian leaders and launched a campaign of Satyagrah moment first time in India. Gandhi's leadership is quite different from all other leaders. In accordance with Ashin Dasgupta, the leadership of Mahatma Gandhi rose from the grass root level and he had always worked for the downtrodden people so that those people also come up and walk straight with the other people. He was a man whose ideology is based on both to the political traditions as well s the Moderates and the Extremists. However, he attempted to give their

² Sarfraz Manzoo, The Guardian, Available at <<https://www.theguardian.com/film/2007/aug/10/india>>

³ Kharingyo shimrah, The Criticism on Gandhi's Politics, Available at <<https://kharingyoshimrah01.wordpress.com/2015/10/08/the-criticism-on-gandhis-poltics/>>

thinking a more practical and dynamic turn. His concept of Swaraj was that of kingdom of God or Ram Rajya that worked for the benefit of the masses.⁴

The Quit India Movement

The moment all started on August 8, 1942 at the time of World War II. The Indian Congress under the Gandhi called mass withdrawal of British and Gandhi's "DO or DIE" speech was the icing on the cake. A new Prime Minister of England offered concessions to the Indian demands as to make the rights which must be based on independent Provincial constitutions and then it was wholly rejected by Indians. This was the time when nation ones again stand as one and entered mass civil disobedience through various speeches. This movement has introduced the idea that British cannot control the Indians. These all things come in air because of the persistent efforts of Mahatma Gandhi.

Struggle of independence and framing Constitution of India: Division of India

India is a country had a very reluctant history of slavery as well as fearlessness. The prominent Indian leaders had done a great job both Garam Dal and Naram Dal to make India independent from the Britishers who ruled over Indian approximately two-hundred years. The debate to form a constitution was started after the independence 1947. The criticism in which the researcher is discussing upon the Mahatma Gandhi all was started at the time of independence and division of India. Mahatma Gandhi was never in favor of division and he wants the united India which must consist only of Indians, he did not want the division of India on the basis of religion in between Hindu and Muslim. The ideology of Gandhi was different he believed in religious harmony. The arguments of Gandhi against the partition were now favored by the people in general now-a-days.

He was the great supporter of unity among the various communities in India. He did not want the separation between Hindu and Muslims, what he wants is the unity among the country. He always used to say that country could be divided over his dead body.⁵ The

⁴ Modern History of India, Available at <<https://www.importantindia.com/21397/role-of-mahatma-gandhi-in-indias-struggle-for-freedom/>>

⁵ Understanding Partition Available at <<https://www.zigya.com/index.php/study/book?class=12&board=cbse&subject=history&book=themes+in+indian+>

arguments which he used to say against the partition was-

- He stated that demand of Muslim League for Pakistan as a separate country was not in accordance with the Islamic law and totally sinful. He also mentioned that Islam stands for unity and brotherhood only.
- In accordance with the Mahatma Gandhi, the protagonists of partition of the country were the enemies of both the religion Islam as well as India.
- He was the only man who not ready to accept the partition of India. Instead he was ready to cut down into pieces.

CONCLUSION

Mahatma Gandhi, the Father of the Nation is now became the hatred among the young Indians. The reason must be astonishing for all. He was being discarded because of his personal life as well as his professional life. The ideology of Gandhi and his Hindu-Muslim unity is one of the major causes which took the life of thousands of Indians as well as Hindus. He always wants his ideology in front. At the time of framing of constitution, he was the one who highlighted the rights of Muslim in advance. He made the statement that he did not want any Muslim suffer because of any misconduct made by him although whatever they did to our people. He always fought the rights of Muslim in this regard. When after framing of constitution of India he was not satisfied as he made the statement that whatever one do must be done in the light of keeping in the mind for downtrodden communities in society. He was also walked away from the Constituent Assembly at the time of division of India and Pakistan and when Nehru became the Prime Minister because he wanted that his dear friend Jinnah became the Prime Minister of India so that India could not divided into two. This was the thing he was greatly criticized among all and the proverb sits here is that, "no one will count your thousands of good things, but your one mistake will lead to end of all the things." So, the reason for which Nathuram Godse was that he was against this non-violence and extra-ordinary ideology of Gandhi which certainly led him to kill the Father of the Nation.

history+iii&chapter=understanding+partition&q_type=&q_topic=&question_id=HSEN12022534&page=1>